

INTEGERS WHICH CANNOT BE PARTITIONED INTO AN EVEN NUMBER OF CONSECUTIVE PARTS

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Abstract

Consider the algebraic torus (as a variety) $X := \mathbb{C}^\times \times \mathbb{C}^\times$ and its Hilbert scheme of n points, denoted $X^{[n]}$. Let $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ be the E-polynomial of the GIT¹ quotient $\tilde{X}^{[n]} := X^{[n]}/G$, where $G := \mathbb{C}^\times \times \mathbb{C}^\times$ is the algebraic torus (as a Lie group) and the action of G on $X^{[n]}$ is induced by the obvious action of G on X . We show a relationship between the coefficients of $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ and the existence of a partition

$$n = m + (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \cdots + (m + k - 1),$$

with $m, k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, such that k even.

1. Introduction

Let $X := \mathbb{C}^\times \times \mathbb{C}^\times$ be the algebraic torus as a variety. Denote $X^{[n]}$ the Hilbert scheme of n points on X . The Lie group $G := \mathbb{C}^\times \times \mathbb{C}^\times$ acts on X in the obvious way. This action can be extended to $X^{[n]}$. So, we can define the GIT quotient $\tilde{X}^{[n]} := X^{[n]}/G$.

The E-polynomial of $\tilde{X}^{[n]}$, denoted $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$, was studied by T. Hausel, E. Letellier and F. Rodriguez-Villegas [4] and independently² by C. Kassel and C. Reutenauer [6, 7, 8]. For more arithmetical results about these polynomials, see [2, 3].

¹GIT is the abbreviation for Geometric Invariant Theory.

²C. Kassel and C. Reutenauer defined $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$, in a rather combinatorial way, as the unique polynomial $P_n(q) = E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ satisfying $(q - 1)^2 P_n(q) = C_n(q)$, where $C_n(q)$ is the number of n -codimensional ideals of the algebra $\mathbb{F}_q[x, y, x^{-1}, y^{-1}]$.

The degree of $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ is $2n - 2$, it is self-reciprocal and all its coefficients are non-negative integers [7], i.e.

$$E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q) = a_{n,0}q^{n-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} a_{n,i} (q^{n-1+i} + q^{n-1-i}), \tag{1}$$

for some nonnegative integers $a_{n,0}, a_{n,1}, a_{n,2}, \dots, a_{n,n-1}$. The aim of this paper is to prove the following result.

Theorem 1. *For each integer $n \geq 1$, the following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) *all odd divisors of n are smaller than $\sqrt{2n}$;*
- (ii) $a_{n,0} \geq a_{n,1} \geq a_{n,2} \geq \dots \geq a_{n,n-1}$;
- (iii) *for all integers $m \geq 1$ and $k \geq 1$, the equality³*

$$n = m + (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \dots + (m + k - 1)$$

implies that k is odd.

It is worth mentioning that a finite sequence s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n is *unimodal* if and only if there is some $1 \leq t \leq n$ such that

$$s_1 \leq s_2 \leq s_3 \leq \dots \leq s_t \geq s_{t+1} \geq s_{t+2} \geq s_{t+3} \geq \dots \geq s_n.$$

A polynomial having non-negative coefficients is said to be *unimodal* if its sequence of coefficients is unimodal. So, if $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ satisfies condition (ii) in Theorem 1, then it is unimodal.

2. Proof of the Main Result

We will use the generating function

$$\prod_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - t^m)^2}{(1 - qt^m)(1 - q^{-1}t^m)} = 1 + (q + q^{-1} - 2) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)}{q^{n-1}} t^n, \tag{2}$$

due to T. Hausel, E. Letellier and F. Rodriguez-Villegas [4] and independently to C. Kassel and C. Reutenauer [6].

³The expression of a number as a sum of consecutive numbers is named *polite representation*.

Lemma 1. *The number of solutions $(m, k) \in (\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1})^2$ of the equation*

$$n = m + (m + 1) + (m + 2) + \cdots + (m + k - 1),$$

with k even, coincides with the number of odd divisors d of n satisfying the inequality $d > \sqrt{2n}$.

Proof. This result is due to M. D. Hirschhorn and P. M. Hirschhorn [5]. □

Lemma 2. *Let $n \geq 1$ be an integer. For any divisor d of $2n$, if $d > \sqrt{2n}$ then*

$$n + \frac{1}{2} \left(d - \frac{2n}{d} - 1 \right) \geq n > n - 1 \geq n + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d - 1 \right) \geq 0.$$

Proof. Consider an integer $n \geq 1$. Let d be a divisor of $2n$. Suppose that $d > \sqrt{2n}$. The inequality $d > \sqrt{2n}$ implies that $d - \frac{2n}{d} > 0$. Using the fact that $d - \frac{2n}{d}$ is an integer, it follows that $d - \frac{2n}{d} \geq 1$. So, $n + \frac{1}{2} \left(d - \frac{2n}{d} - 1 \right) \geq n$.

The inequality $d - \frac{2n}{d} > 0$ implies that $\frac{2n}{d} - d < 0$. Using the fact that $\frac{2n}{d} - d$ is an integer, it follows that $\frac{2n}{d} - d \leq -1$. So, $n + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d - 1 \right) \leq n - 1$.

For $x \geq 1$ and $y \geq 1$, we have the trivial inequality

$$(x - 1)(y - 1) \geq 2(1 - y).$$

From the above inequality, it follows that $xy \geq x - y + 1$. Substituting $x = d$ and $y = \frac{2n}{d}$, we obtain

$$2n \geq d - \frac{2n}{d} + 1,$$

which is equivalent to

$$n + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d - 1 \right) \geq 0.$$

□

Lemma 3. *Let $n \geq 1$ be an integer. For any divisor d of $2n$, if $d < \sqrt{2n}$, then*

$$n + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d - 1 \right) \geq n > n - 1 \geq n + \frac{1}{2} \left(d - \frac{2n}{d} - 1 \right) \geq 0.$$

Proof. It is enough to apply Lemma 2 with $d = \frac{2n}{d}$. □

We proceed to prove our main result.

Proof. (Theorem 1) The equality

$$E \left(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q \right) = \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{2}}} \frac{q^{n+(2n/d-d-1)/2} - q^{n+(d-2n/d-1)/2}}{q - 1}$$

follows from the combination of (2) with the classical identity [4, p. 113]

$$\frac{1}{\theta(w)} - \frac{1}{1-w} = \sum_{\substack{n, m \geq 1 \\ n \not\equiv m \pmod{2}}} (-1)^n q^{nm/2} w^{(m-n-1)/2},$$

attributed to L. Kronecker and C. Jordan, where $\theta(w)$ is the formal product

$$\theta(w) := (1-w) \prod_{n \geq 1} \frac{(1-q^n w)(1-q^n w^{-1})}{(1-q^n)^2}.$$

We can express $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$ as the difference $E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q) = R_n(q) - S_n(q)$ of two polynomials given by⁴

$$S_n(q) = \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ d > \sqrt{2n}}} \frac{q^{n+(d-2n/d-1)/2} - q^{n+(2n/d-d-1)/2}}{q-1},$$

$$R_n(q) = \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ d < \sqrt{2n}}} \frac{q^{n+(2n/d-d-1)/2} - q^{n+(d-2n/d-1)/2}}{q-1}.$$

Applying Lemmas 2 and 3, the coefficients of $S_n(q)$ and $R_n(q)$ are non-negative integers. Using the expansion $\frac{q^n-1}{q-1} = 1 + q + q^2 + \dots + q^{n-1}$, it follows from the explicit formulae for $S_n(q)$ and $R_n(q)$ that the coefficients from (1) can be expressed as $a_{n,i} = a_{n,i}^+ - a_{n,i}^-$, where

$$a_{n,i}^+ = \# \left\{ d|n : d \text{ odd}, d < \sqrt{2n}, i \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d - 1 \right) \right\},$$

$$a_{n,i}^- = \# \left\{ d|n : d \text{ odd}, d > \sqrt{2n}, i \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(d - \frac{2n}{d} - 1 \right) \right\}.$$

Notice that the functions $\mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, given by $i \mapsto a_{n,i}^+$ and $i \mapsto a_{n,i}^-$, are both weakly decreasing⁵. Hence, condition (ii) holds provided that $d < \sqrt{2n}$ for each odd divisor d of n , because in this case, $a_{n,i}^- = 0$ for all i .

Suppose that $d_0 > \sqrt{2n}$ for a fixed odd divisor d_0 of n . On the one hand, $a_{n,i_0}^- > a_{n,i_0+1}^-$, where $i_0 := \frac{1}{2} \left(d_0 - \frac{2n}{d_0} - 1 \right)$. On the other hand, $a_{n,i_0}^+ = a_{n,i_0+1}^+$, because the equality $\frac{1}{2} \left(d_0 - \frac{2n}{d_0} - 1 \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d_0} - d_0 - 1 \right)$ is impossible⁶ for any odd

⁴Notice that, if $d = \sqrt{2n}$, for some integer d , then d is even.

⁵A sequence s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n is *weakly decreasing* if $s_1 \geq s_2 \geq \dots \geq s_n$.

⁶This equality would imply that the product $d d_0 = 2n$ is even, while both d_0 and d are odd.

divisor d of n . So, $a_{n,i_0} < a_{n,i_0+1}$. Hence, condition (ii) does not hold provided that there is at least one odd divisor d of n satisfying $d > \sqrt{2n}$.

In virtue of Lemma 1, we conclude that conditions (iii) and (ii) are equivalent. The equivalence between (i) and (iii) follows by Lemma 1. \square

3. Final Remarks

Consider the symmetric Dyck word [1] $\langle\langle n \rangle\rangle := w_1 w_2 \cdots w_k \in \{+, -\}^*$, whose letters are given by

$$w_i := \begin{cases} +, & \text{if } u_i \in D_n \setminus (2D_n); \\ -, & \text{if } u_i \in (2D_n) \setminus D_n; \end{cases}$$

where D_n is the set of divisors of n , $2D_n := \{2d : d \in D_n\}$ and u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k are the elements of the symmetric difference $D_n \Delta 2D_n$ written in increasing order. This word encodes the non-zero coefficients of $(q-1)E(\tilde{X}^{[n]}; q)$. Theorem 1 admits the language-theoretical reformulation: condition (iii) is equivalent to $\langle\langle n \rangle\rangle = \underbrace{+\cdots+}_{s \text{ times}} \underbrace{-\cdots-}_{s \text{ times}}$, for some $s \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. For details, see [1].

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